

The role of Makerspaces for crisis-affected communities: benefits and challenges

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Abstract

The number of Makerspaces around the world has grown exponentially in recent years. These creative spaces offers non-expert users the opportunity to engage with digital fabrication tools alongside traditional craft tools. Recently, the humanitarian sector has become interested in Makerspaces as a way to empower people to meet their own needs. A number of Makerspaces specifically aimed at crisis-affected communities have emerged. However, to date there has been virtually no research on how these spaces operate. The current research addresses this gap and documents the results of an ongoing study. This study conducts interviews with five providers of Makerspaces for crisis-affected people, using grounded theory to reveal the benefits and challenges of operating these spaces. In addition, a systems thinking lens is applied to identify common problem-generating patterns across the four Makerspaces investigated in the study. This study has practical implications for the management of Makerspaces for crisis-affected people. It also reveals the need to understand the behaviour of the Makerspaces in more detail in order to identify further opportunities to counteract the challenges highlighted. Future research will validate current findings with other perspectives, from users and other contexts.

Keywords

Makerspaces, digital fabrication, humanitarian, crisis-affected communities

1 Introduction

In the period since Gershenfeld (2012) declared a digital revolution, access to digital fabrication tools in Makerspaces has grown dramatically. At the same time, natural and man-made disasters resulting from climate change, environmental damage and conflict, are all contributing to a rise in humanitarian demand (HLP, 2015).

Recently, there is increasing interest in how crisis-affected communities can engage with innovation (Betts et al., 2015). This has in part, been driven by the recognition of the creative and adaptive potential of people living in limited-resource contexts, as found in literature on frugal innovation (Radjou et al., 2012; Prabhu, 2017). Frugal innovation describes the innovative practices of non-expert designers who make do with limited resources. This type of ‘bottom-up’ design, which is driven by the end user, promises greater empowerment by allowing people to find solutions for their own problems.

Lately, there have been a number of efforts to engage with innovation from the humanitarian sector. This is reflected in the emergence of Makerspaces, targeted at providing resources for crisis-affected communities. Despite the growing number of these spaces, there is relatively little understanding about how they operate, their potential benefits and the barriers to their work. To date, the majority of research

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on Makerspaces has focused on their presence in high-resource settings (HRSs), whereas Makerspaces for crisis-affected communities are typically found in low-resource settings (LRSs). Contextual differences mean that it cannot be assumed that socio-technical systems are replicable from HRSs to LRSs (Jagtap et al., 2014).

The current study addresses this gap in knowledge and asks a number of questions. How do these Makerspaces work? What opportunities do Makerspaces offer crisis-affected communities? What are the barriers that limit these areas? What kinds of infrastructure and ecosystems are needed to support their development? This paper documents the results of an ongoing study. It includes an interview study with five individuals who are responsible for the management or operational activities of four Makerspaces that provide resources for crisis-affected people in: Greece, Jordan and Nepal. The second part of the ongoing study, which is not yet completed, will engage with the users of these Makerspaces in order to further understand how these spaces operate.

The paper is structured as follows. First, an explanation of the methodological approach taken in the research. Second, a presentation of the research findings, which reveals five key benefits offered by Makerspaces. Third, taking a comparative approach, the research identifies the barriers that limit the impact of Makerspaces. Next, using systems thinking to analyse these barriers, the study reveals three systems archetypes which present challenges to the current operations of Makerspaces for crisis-affected communities. Finally, there is a discussion of the practical implications of the findings and areas for future research are highlighted.

2 Methods

This research takes a grounded theory approach (Corbin and Strauss, 1990) which starts with empirical data as opposed to existing literature. As the emergence of Makerspaces for crisis-affected communities is a relatively new phenomena, this method is chosen as a suitable approach for building theory. Five people who are involved in the management or operational activities of Makerspaces for crisis-affected communities were interviewed using semi-structured interviews. They were identified through online searches and recommendations from colleagues. Table 1 provides an overview of the participants who were interviewed.

All interviews were conducted over skype, which were audio recorded and complemented with note-taking. All the recordings were taken with the interviewee's consent and were recorded verbatim afterwards. All the interviews were conducted by the first author and lasted an average of one hour. The semi-structured interviews were guided by thematic questions in three parts. First, the interviewee was asked to describe the Makerspace, providing a description of the facilities and community of users. Second, the interviewee was asked about the potential benefits of Makerspaces for crisis-affected communities, reflecting on the short term and long term goals of the organisation. Finally, the interviewee was asked to identify some of the challenges that limited their work.

All interviewees were informed about the purpose of the research before starting the interview and they were also given the opportunity to ask question and provide additional comments at the end of the interview.

The interview transcripts were imported into the qualitative data analysis software, MAXQDA. To begin with, line by line *open* coding was completed with particular attention focused on identifying potential benefits and constraints of Makerspaces for crisis-affected communities. Descriptive coding provided a summary of a basic theme or coded segment. On first iteration the transcripts were divided into 127 coded segments, coded against 42 codes. For example, the coded segment: "*It's about empowering and providing agency to affected communities*" was coded as 'community empowerment'. After all the open codes were completed a process of grouping conceptually similar codes was conducted in *axial* coding. For example, 'community empowerment', 'skills development', 'changing perceptions' and 'self-confidence' were grouped together to form the higher category 'identity renewal and personal development'. Finally, selective coding was undertaken, to compare and examine the relationships between open and axial codes. The codes were grouped into two categories: benefits and challenges of Makerspaces for crisis affected communities.

Following this analysis, the transcripts were reviewed again, using a systems thinking lens to identify potential archetypes in the cases described. Systems thinking archetypes characterise a set of common patterns or behaviours in systems (Meadows, 2008). By first, understanding how the system behaves, it is possible to identify the underlying reasons for its behaviour. This provides a starting point for future interventions to alter the system's behaviour.

#	Makerspace	Role	Location	Target user group
1	Makerspace 1	CEO	Greece	Refugees
2	Makerspace 2	Innovation research analyst	Greece	Refugees
3	Makerspace 2	Co-founder	Greece	Refugees
4	Makerspace 3	Co-founder	Jordan	Refugees
5	Makerspace 4	Executive director	Nepal	Earthquake affected population

Table 5: Overview of participants interviewed.

3 Results

The following section presents the results of the study so far, which documents the perspectives of the Makerspace providers. First, the benefits offered by Makerspaces to crisis-affected communities are presented in five themes: (1) identity renewal and personal development; (2) community integration; (3) bottom-up design; (4) social innovation; and (5) livelihoods. Second, major challenges of operating Makerspaces are identified: (1) providing training and skills development; (2) fostering communities of users; (3) access to funding; and (4) challenging mind sets. Finally a systems thinking lens is applied to identify patterns of behaviour across the four Makerspaces investigated. These patterns are described in the form of three systems archetypes.

3.1 Benefits offered by Makerspaces to crisis-affected communities

All of the participants identified that Makerspaces provide potential for the *identity renewal and personal development* of users. Users learn design and making skills as they engage with new tools and materials, as well as developing personal skills in communication, resilience and cooperation. More importantly, these spaces facilitate transformations in the users' personal identity. This is noted in both the growth of self-confidence among users, as well as the changing attitudes towards the users from the wider community.

"It's a radical shift in the way people perceive themselves in society and how enabled they are in achieving their means." (Interviewee 1)

"It's about empowering and proving agency to affected communities." (Interviewee 4)

This identity renewal and growth is particularly important for individuals who have been affected by crisis, who experience frustration, boredom and inactivity (Stearns, 2011). By enabling the users to direct their own learning, individuals are empowered in a way that shifts them from dependency to agency. Such findings are consistent with research on the role of Makerspaces for at-risk youth, which documents the importance of Makerspaces in building trust, commitment and self-confidence (Hughes, 2017).

Second, these spaces offer the potential for *community integration*, by creating a community of users who are embedded in a wider ecosystem. By supporting relationships between crisis-affected groups of people, communities are more resilient and adaptable (Powley, 2009). Additionally, for displaced people, these spaces provide a safe space in which they can interact with and build relationships with people from the host community. Notably, this tackles potential resentment towards the crisis-affected community by the host community, resulting from the perceived strain on local resources to support displaced people

(de la Chaux and Haughes, 2014). The participants point out how community integration can operate at both local and international levels. The existing collaborative network of Makerspaces provides a foundation for community integration in different countries. In this way, Makerspaces behave as facilitators for social and support networks.

“So in Greece there are these refugees and they are transitioning to other countries, Germany and France, for example. And in fact they might arrive to some cities and there might be a fab lab... for them to be continuously supported through other fab labs... to enter into a network of support wherever they arrive.” (Interviewee 2)

Third, the Makerspaces offer the potential *bottom-up design*. By recognising the creativity and skills of crisis-affected communities, it is possible that users can develop solutions to meet their own needs. For many of the interviewees, bottom-up design was viewed as a corollary to empowerment and identity renewal.

“You want to return dignity back to vulnerable populations. How do you do that? By helping them find their own solutions.” (Interviewee 1)

Although this is an area with significant potential identified by the participants, there were relatively few examples of bottom-up design in action. One potential barrier is the time required for skills development and training. Another barrier considered is that expressing this opportunity to aid agencies is challenging. Further support is needed in this area to exploit this benefit.

The fourth benefit of Makerspaces that participants identified for crisis-affected users is *social innovation*. In this sense, Makerspaces are not just about nurturing technical skills, but are strongly focused on mobilising social resources, such as creativity, communication and innovation. As such Makerspaces offer the potential for more hybrid learning and engagement, by combining traditional, craft and digital skills. This multi-disciplinary approach is naturally inclusive and encourages a greater diversity of users (Sheridan et al., 2014). Thus, Makerspaces can be viewed as catalysts for *social innovation*.

“It’s not only about having the technology, but it’s about what you do with it, how you solve problems” (Interviewee 3)

“So it’s not just about tech and innovation, but more about creativity and the arts and community building. So we’re also a space that allows people to do screenings of documentary films. We also have murals and graffiti art and we are trying to get community workshops happening on a more frequent basis for young people and adults and educators. So if anyone has an idea of what they would like to do, we would like to incorporate that into our space somehow and see how we could make it a part of our project.” (Interviewee 5)

Lastly, the participants spoke about the potential for Makerspaces to sustain *livelihoods*. The participants described how the spaces allow for individuals to develop ideas into solutions that are commercially viable. Such views are consistent with literature on market-based development which proposes that poverty alleviation can occur through the development of new economies (Fisher, 2006). Supporting livelihoods is noted as a key activity to prevent crisis-affected people from seeking work in potentially unsafe environments.

“So there is this plan in Burkina Faso to provide an alternative for gold mining for youths... there are all sort of dangers and risks associated with that kind of work... so that idea is to set up an environment, to provide an alternative... which would attract them more than going to the gold mine, and offer them potentially an interesting future as well.” (Interviewee 3)

Moreover, supporting livelihoods and local economic development, is noted as an important way of countering the brain-drain among crisis-affected communities (Taylor et al. 2011). Broadly, these approaches are seen as part of a longer term strategy to overcome social challenges.

“So now I think there’s more of an interest in economic development, to strengthen the private sector, to retain talented, young Nepali so that they are not leaving... we are trying to create very conducive ecosystems to support them... it’s more about long term development and how innovation helps to address these long term, engrained social challenges” (Interviewee 5)

3.2 Challenges that limit the impact of Makerspaces for crisis-affected communities

Lastly, the participants spoke about the potential for Makerspaces to sustain *livelihoods*. The participants described how the spaces allow for individuals to develop ideas into solutions that are commercially viable. Such views are consistent with literature on market-based development which proposes that poverty alleviation can occur through the development of new economies (Fisher, 2006). Supporting livelihoods is noted as a key activity to prevent crisis-affected people from seeking work in potentially unsafe environments.

The first challenge identified by the interviewees was around providing *training and skills development* programs to users. In some cases, providers were unsure about the type of training that was most appropriate for users. In other cases, they described the gap between people receiving training and people confidently using tools. This was also noted in their concerns that tools – particularly digital technologies – were not being used regularly in the Makerspace.

“We’re not seeing some of the people come back to use the equipment after they’ve been trained.” (Interviewee 5)

Additionally, the lack of skills in the community adds a burden for the management of these spaces. In general, Makerspaces rely on a community of users to collaborate, transfer knowledge and maintain the space (Robbins and Smith, 2016). There is a need to foster a *community of users* to support these environments becoming more self-sufficient. Without a group of skilled users who are engaged with wanting to help the wider community of users, there is significant constraint of the sustainability of these spaces. As Hatch (2014) points out, Makerspaces are more than just providing physical resources, but should focus on cultivating *give*, whereby people want to actively share and collaborate.

“You have these geniuses who know how to do X, Y, Z. They don’t want to work in a lab [Makerspace], to be a member of staff, but they’ll use the lab to build stuff... they’re happy to set up shop, to start a company, but working in a lab is a lot about teaching and community development... we want to have it become something that is much more sustainable and have the community itself to really want to invest in keeping it going.” (Interviewee 4)

Another challenge identified by the participants was the lack of *accessible funding* to support the development of these Makerspaces. For the providers interviewed they often related funding constraints to the need to challenge *mind sets* in the sector. In particular they believed that the difficulty finding funding was a result of the lack of understanding about innovation and the role of digital fabrication in the humanitarian sector.

“The humanitarian sector is not really up to speed. People think 3D printing is cool but they don’t really understand it. So getting funding is tough, getting funding for innovation is tough, getting funding for innovation in the humanitarian sector is really hard. There’s this and there’s this, but it’s a drop in a bucket.” (Interviewee 4)

This draws attention for the need for more detailed research that documents how these Makerspaces for crisis-affected communities work in order to disseminate knowledge in the humanitarian sector. Another interviewee comments that mind sets can be challenged through a virtuous cycle of proving impact.

“I think that if we have at least two or three good stories of amazing companies or products that came out, it would also create a shift in the society” (Interviewee 1)

Regardless, these Makerspaces will still operate within resource constrained environments and require lean financial models to be scalable and sustainable. This approach is being explored in the second Makerspace in this study, which is supporting the research of self-replicating CNC machines in order to reduce the cost of machinery for future Makerspaces.

3.3 Systems archetypes

Systems thinking offers a way of understanding the relationships between a system’s structure and behaviour (Senge, 1990; Medows, 2008; Strohm, 2015). In order to define a desired future, it is necessary to first understand how a system works. This provides a foundation for achieving more desirable behaviour patterns in the future. Typical problem-generating sets of behaviours have been identified as

a number of *systems archetypes* by Meadows (2008). By recognising these archetypes it is possible to adjust the system in order to eliminate the problems that result.

The relationships between the benefits and challenges identified by the participants were reviewed and a comparative approach was taken to analyse patterns across the four Makerspaces investigated. This revealed three systems archetypes: (1) drifting goals; (2) limits to growth; and (3) success to the successful.

3.3.1 Drifting goals

The participants interviewed revealed that the Makerspaces were subject to drifting goals. This describes the response of lowering the overall goal of the system in reaction to challenges faced. For example, interviewee 5 pointed out that the 3D printer and tools in the space were rarely used by the community, despite the fact that engaging the community with technology was an initial aim of the Makerspace. The interviewee suggested that engagement with these technologies was now a less important focus for the space.

In some instances, the shift in goals is influenced by external factors. For example, interviewee 2 and 3, described the need to adjust goals according to the changing demographic of users arriving at the space.

“The fact that we had a target population of accompanied minors at the beginning of a particular age range and then we started to see that the population started to arrive, mostly younger kids with adults and the dynamics in the space had to change of course.” (Interviewee 2)

Of course, in some cases goals must be adjusted in response to changes or new learnings. However, this archetype draws attention to the need for keeping absolute performance standards. In general, the interviewees did not have specific goals for expected impact of the space, as the majority of the Makerspaces were still operating in a fairly exploratory phase.

3.3.2 Limits to growth

Second, the participants identified many *limits to growth* that constrain the development of the Makerspaces. In particular these limits were identified as availability of funding and resistance to change from the humanitarian sector. Additional limits were also identified as *logistics* and *political* challenges. In the case of one Makerspace, logistics challenges and customs delays meant that the Makerspace opened without all the equipment needed at the start.

“So when all the equipment got there, given that it wasn’t going to a UN agency, there was a different tax regime. And then we had a lot of the equipment blocked at customs, so it made the process a bit tedious at the start.” (Interviewee 2)

Moreover, it was noted that in some contexts, governmental constraints prevented the Makerspaces from the achieving their desired goals.

“We started out to establish a fab lab in a refugee camp in Zataari and the idea was to improve self-efficiency in refugee camps and to reduce the burden on communities. And that didn’t happen...well a lot of political things happened” (Interviewee 4)

In order to fully explore the benefits of these Makerspaces, it is important to address these financial, political and logistical limits.

3.3.3 Success to the successful

The final archetype describes a concern that these spaces may struggle to deliver benefits to the most at-risk individuals. In this sense, *success to the successful* refers to the idea that the benefits of the Makerspaces are only transferred to the most privileged users. One concern for Makerspaces set up in refugee affected areas, is that they are mostly being used by the host community as opposed to the crisis-affected community for which they were intended. Similar concerns about inclusivity are voiced at the Makerspace for earthquake affected people in Nepal.

“But we ended up supporting the establishment of a lab which is like 25 minutes away from the camp, which theoretically is supposed be accessible to refugees in the camp and nearby, as well as Jordanians ... There’s this whole migration issue, so it’s very difficult to get anything done. Especially anything that’s new or innovative, then why aren’t you doing it for the host community. So normally we do it for both and then the host community just takes over.” (Interviewee 4)

However, it was noted that in one Makerspace, there had been positive results for the inclusivity of women and girls. Further investigation of the drivers behind inclusivity in these spaces is needed to address this potential challenge.

“one of our objectives was to increase participation and attendance of women and girls... And so far we have had participation of 54% more women than of men.” (Interviewee 2)

4 Discussion

This paper has presented the findings of an ongoing study into the role of Makerspaces for crisis-affected communities. It has revealed the perspectives of five people responsible for the management or organisation of four Makerspaces in Greece, Jordan and Nepal. As part of this project, further research will be conducted to identify the perspectives of users. These perspectives will allow for comparison and validation of the benefits and limitations of Makerspaces that have been identified in this study. Documenting the perspectives of crisis-affected communities is fundamental to understanding the extent to which these perceived benefits and limitation affect the users themselves. Reflecting on some of the bottom-up approaches discussed in this study, the authors acknowledge the capabilities of crisis-affected people to direct their own experiences.

So far, this study has shown that Makerspaces offer significant potential benefits to crisis-affected communities. These benefits can be realised in the development of tangible design and making skills, as well as both intra- and inter-personal skills, such as motivation, self-efficacy and cooperation. This is consistent with constructionist theories of learning that describe how learning evolves through real world experiences (Papert, 1980, 1993). Similarly, Katterfeldt et al. (2015) formalise the concept of *bildung* in making whereby, a deep learning process takes place that results in a change within the individual as they interact with their environment. In this sense, users of the Makerspaces are expected not only to learn about tools and materials, but are also called upon to explore their identity and relationship to the wider community.

The extent of community integration needs to be further investigated. Certainly for these spaces to operate as functional Makerspaces, there is a need to cultivate environments that embrace community and inclusion. As Branigan-Pipe (2017) points out, Makerspaces should be environments that respect the varying needs of people regardless of age, race, religion, gender, or learning ability. Makerspaces need to be especially mindful of this, giving particular attention to the systems archetype identified: *success to the successful*. This leads to the following questions for future research: How are communities formed in Makerspaces for crisis-affected people? What are the factors that support or limit inclusivity in these spaces?

As well as providing a space for personal development and community enablement, Makerspaces have been shown to facilitate the development of tangible solutions that can support *social innovation, bottom-up design* and *livelihoods*. In the cases identified, these opportunities had mostly not yet been realised. In part, this can be understood through the challenges noted as *limits to growth*. In particular there is a need for wider dissemination about the value of Makerspaces in the humanitarian sector. This is believed to be an important enabler for challenging mind sets and helping to improve access to funding. Aligning goals across all stakeholders, including local government, will also be important for overcoming some of the political and logistics challenges identified. Notably, the current research draws attention to the pitfall of *drifting goals* that are a particular risk during the early stages of these Makerspaces, when the goals themselves are not clearly established.

Finally, in order to support the potential for more user-driven design and making, there is a need to develop local design and innovation capacities. Training and skills development was noted as a major barrier for the Makerspaces, which underlines the need for more understanding about the most effective types of training. Future research should consider lessons learned in this area from other contexts, including developed countries. Despite the significantly different contexts, a comparative analysis might provide possible starting points for developing appropriate training programmes. One observation from the study, is that the interviewees did not sufficiently explain specifically why the digital technologies provided in the Makerspaces enabled impact. It would be interesting to compare these Makerspaces,

which are enabled with digital technologies, to other non-digital and community interventions for crisis-affected people.

5 Conclusion

To date, there has been relatively little understanding about how Makerspaces for crisis-affected communities operate. This research documents the first stage in an exploratory study, using qualitative methods to gather and analyse four Makerspaces in Greece, Jordan and Nepal, from the perspectives of Makerspace providers. The research identifies some of the benefits offered to crisis-affected communities by these Makerspaces, and also outlines some of the challenges which limit the impact of these spaces. Three systems archetypes are also presented which reveal types of problematic behaviour common to the Makerspaces. The study also points out areas for further research. There is a need to validate the findings with other perspectives, from users and other contexts. In particular, there is a need for more in-depth research that explores the drivers behind the behaviour of these Makerspaces in order to identify detailed opportunities to counteract the problem-generating archetypes identified. Such research will be critical for the sustainable development of Makerspaces for crisis-affected communities.

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Lucia Corsini, James Moultrie: The role of Makerspaces for crisis-affected communities: benefits and challenges

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